

EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATION ON THE PERFORMANCE OF CARBON-EPOXY LAMINATES CONTAINING GAPS AND OVERLAPS FABRICATED BY AUTOMATED FIBER PLACEMENT

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ABSTRACT

Manufacturers use Automated Fiber Placement (AFP) as a fabrication process for large and complex composite parts. AFP shows great potential to transition from hand layup to an automated technique [1, 2]. An AFP machine consists of a computer-controlled robotic arm with a head at the end capable of constant placement of uncured preimpregnated carbon fibers grouped together to form bands called tows. AFP machines control orientation of fibers placed onto a mold to build the layup, but this method also creates defects which undermine the structural performance of the part [3]. Primary defects observed by the aerospace industry are gaps and overlaps. Corresponding detection methods are labor intensive and time consuming [4]. Proposed in this paper is an investigation on the effect of size and distribution of half gap / half overlap on mechanical performance of composite structures made with AFP techniques. The goal of this research is to better assess the strain-stress response subjected to both tensile and compression loading of such composite structures. By varying the orientation, size and number of defects embedded in carbon-epoxy laminates, the effects of defects on tensile and compression performance have been experimentally examined to finally draw design guidelines. A Finite Element model has been developed to predict the mechanical behavior of laminates with embedded defects. Without out of waviness geometrical consideration, this FE model is overpredicting strength in case of defects oriented in the direction of the load, and underpredicting strength in case of defects in transverse direction of the load which shows the importance of out of plane waviness.

1. INTRODUCTION

The manufacturing capabilities for the aerospace industry are developing faster than the understanding of composite material damage tolerance. Thus, certification of such structures made by Automated Fiber Placement is a challenge for leading companies investing in this technology. Without the full knowledge of inherent flaws happening in the fabrication process of complex geometries, all the positive outcome of composite use for light weight and higher performance aircrafts is not achieved. The need of a design shift from high margins of safety to optimized design of composite structures is tackled by this research. Progress in the performance of composites

structures requires a better understanding of their mechanical behavior leading to better design and mass savings.

The complexity of the AFP process to manufacture curved shape aircraft fuselage parts presents a high risk of defect generation. The AFP machine controls every tow consisting of a tape, generally made up of 8 to 32 tows. Newer machines can even control the feed rate of each tow individually and can also cut and restart each tow individually. Compaction, heating, cutting and clamping of separate tows are actions done at high speed while the fiber is pulled along a specific fiber path. Steering of fibers allows fibers to follow part curvature geometry but it also induces small buckling in the tows. Outer fibres of steered tows are under tension while fibers on the inside of the curvature path are under compression which affects the mechanical properties. Steering can be responsible for the misalignment of tows leading to side to side half gap / half overlap defects. Corresponding detection methods are labor intensive and time consuming [4]. Once defects are detected, both repair or rejection of AFP-made parts are important investment decisions. According to our industrial partner, the occurrence of half gap / half overlaps generated by steering makes these defects of major interest in the understanding of the performance of AFP manufactured parts. Other types of defects are not as often encountered as the half gap / half overlap during close inspection of an AFP made fuselage, as shown by Bell Helicopter in a study in 2015. [12]

<i>Defect type</i>	<i>Average percentage of total defects</i>
<i>Material & processing</i>	9.55%
<i>Half gap / half overlap</i>	57.07%
<i>Wrinkling</i>	12.90%
<i>Bridging</i>	12.54%
<i>Design related defects</i>	7.95%

Table 1 Defect occurrence - Bell Helicopter [12]

These defects can appear when the computer-controlled head is tape-laying down a complex shaped area of a fuselage, especially when the curvature is important. The steering capabilities of the AFP process are dependent to both the AFP machine and the fiber parameters. Also, the tolerance in the fiber placement head movement, steered fibers, and tow width variation contribute to the introduction of gaps and overlaps [1].

<i>Parameter</i>	<i>Consequences</i>
<i>Creel temperature</i>	Ease feeding of tow in AFP head
<i>Fiber tension</i>	Affect part & tow placement quality
<i>Compression</i>	Cohesion between plies
<i>Heating</i>	Part quality & stiffness
<i>Laydown speed</i>	Fiber impregnation by resin
<i>Fiber tackiness</i>	Part quality & cohesion between plies

Table 2 Manufacturing parameter & consequences

The appearance of half gap / half overlap defect due to steering happens at the intertow area of a tape, before compaction, and at the interband area – adjoining tapes – due to the lack of accuracy in the lay down process of the AFP machine. These defects create both reduction of strength and a change of stiffness compared to pristine conditions. The defects being examined occur when one of

the tows are misaligned. It is important to understand how the size and distribution of such gaps and overlaps influences the strength and failure development.

Recent research developments were made on this subject, for instance Sawicki and Minguet [5] studied the reduction in strength in compression of composite carbon fibers specimens with embedded gaps aligned at a 90° ply orientation. Croft et al. [6] investigated the influence of gaps, overlaps and half gap / half overlaps embedded at the symmetry of laminates under tension, compression and in-plane shear loading tests. Elsherbini and Hoa [7] showed similar trends with respect to fatigue loading. Locally, gaps reduce axial stiffness of laminates due to the missing fibers without greatly affecting the global stiffness. Gap density has a linear effect on laminate stiffness while orientation and location have a non-linear effect on laminate stiffness. Overlaps induce waviness on adjacent plies – extra material due to shifted tows – which does not have significant changes on stiffness [5, 6]. Overlaps can locally improve the strength of laminates. Combination of both side-to-side gaps and overlaps shows a strong out-of-plane influence, making laminate strength prediction much more difficult to assess. Description of the fracture mechanism is made through an analysis of the delamination growth in a specimen with embedded defects.

Intensive research was done on the interaction of gaps and overlaps and their permutations through tested specimens but they still represent a small number of all possible configurations. Generally, multiple defects are required before significant changes begin to happen. Most of the work was carried out on the elaboration of models with much less emphasis on experiments themselves [8]. Unfortunately, most of these studies do not accurately represent the geometry of a steered tow created a half gap / half overlap defect. In past studies, gaps were sometimes called “dropped tows” since they spanned the entirety of the part. Similarly, the overlap geometry was also not always representative. This paper is putting emphasis on what realistically occurs in AFP manufacturing. This means that the geometry presented earlier in this paper for a half gap/overlap is of particular interest.

The approach followed by this research is based on integration of both experiments and Finite-Element modelling. This paper shows the investigation of defects by establishing a close-to-reality test plan allowing the analysis of orientation, location, and size of defects embedded in tested specimens. Each specimen is documented, especially its failure mode under both tension and compression loading. At the time this paper is being written, work is underway to simulate specimens with all configurations of half gap / half overlap defects and to verify experimental results. This FEA model aims to predict both structural behavior at the defect level and crack initiation and propagation. This model is a first step to a fully virtual strength prediction tool for composite components made by AFP, which could eventually lead to a virtual optimization tool. It will allow less experimenting and pave the way for virtual certification techniques of AFP manufacturing process [8].

This paper emphasizes the experimental approach for defect generation, the testing procedure that is followed and finally a detailed analysis of the results in both static tension and compression.

2. TEST PLAN & MANUFACTURING

2.1. Specimen & manufacturing

Specimens are carbon fiber-reinforced epoxy composite laminates following a Quasi-Isotropic layup of 16 plies to which we add one ply of fabric composite at the top and bottom, leading to an 18 ply-laminate. The AFP unidirectional prepreg is T800S/3900-2C and the cross ply woven fabric is

very similar to T400/3900-2. The fabric layers are added since it is a standard practice in industry. The layup is $[45F/(-45T/0T/45T/90T)_2]_s$. Specimens are manufactured with an Automated Fiber Tape (AFT) machine at the National Research Council center in Montreal. An AFT machine works exactly the same way as an AFP machine but tows are not independently controlled. Since our panels are flat this makes no difference in the laying down process. Defects are manually added to the laminate by stopping the AFT machine at each ply of interest, cutting the tow we want to steer, and replacing it under the correct shape and geometry with the use of a solid pattern as a guide. The cure of all AFT manufactured panels was done at Stelia Aerospace using Bell Helicopter requirements. Hard tooling with caul plates was used to get a homogeneous thickness throughout the specimen, regardless of the presence of defects. This tooling minimizes the waviness especially at the defect area.

2.2. Half gap / half overlap

Previous studies were performed on idealized geometries, where overlaps and gaps were rectangular blocks of superimposed and missing tows, respectively, spanning the entire width of the specimen. Moreover, processing changes the geometry of those defects of the composite part by squeezing flow and bleeding flow due to debulking during the manufacturing process and heating and compaction during the cure [9].

The defect geometry that was chosen in our set of experiments has never been done in previous work even though it is commonly seen in industry as the closest representation possible of true half gap / half overlap defect made by an AFP machine. The defects being examined occur when one of the tows becomes misaligned. The tow momentarily crosses over onto the tow beside it. The overlap section has a larger fiber content ratio than the pristine prepreg tape. In the end, the half gap / half overlap defect ends up having a trapezoidal shape.

Figure 1 Half gap / half overlap defect geometry [13]

The general shape of the half gap/overlap defect shown in Figure 1 has many parameters that can be changed such as length, width, curvature of the ends, etc. The length of the defects is fixed in order to fit the largest available test fixture. The total length of the defects is 2.5in (63.5mm). Defect width is also a parameter, varied between two values: 0.05in and 0.1in (1.27mm and 2.54mm).

In reality, more permutations of different sizes happen during both the laying down process of tows and the cure of the composite parts. Modeling offers the possibility to test more configurations to finally optimize the parameters and minimize the effects of the defects. It is the next step of this research.

It is also important to consider the edge effects when looking at composite laminate testing. Edge effects refer to the increase of normal stress along the edge of the parts. This phenomenon has been studied on various occasions. In 1995, Lessard et al [10] performed a study and compared it with previous results. Tips of defects are consequently located at a minimum of twice the specimen thickness to the coupon edges. Then, considering ASTM D6484 and ASTM D3039 used for, respectively, the static compression and tension, we define the dimensions of our coupons. There are two sizes of coupons. Both configurations with 0° oriented defects and pristine are 12in (304.8mm) long and 1.5in (38.1mm) wide. Other configurations use wider coupons, 3in (76.2mm) wide. This choice was made to save time and material since we don't need wide coupons for plies oriented in 0° because defects are aligned on the length of the specimens. Different fixtures, grips and wedges were used depending the width of the coupon.

2.3. Test plan

A naming convention was created in order to be more concise when writing. The rule for the naming convention as well as a table listing every coupon can be seen in Table 5. This test plan tends to have worse case scenarios configurations with a superimposed sequence of defects that would probably not happen in a real-life manufactured part. This test plan was designed to understand the effect of defect geometrical parameters introduced previously. This choice of tested configurations in tension and compression also assures to have a broad panel of defect orientation which will allow verification of the FEA model being written.

13 different configurations with varying defect sizes – from 0.05in (1.27mm) to 0.1in (2.54mm) width gap – and distributions – 4, 7, 10 defects through the thickness of the laminate – of defects were manually embedded in composite coupons in different ply orientations – 0°, 45°, 90° – in order to assess their effects on the performance of the final part. The onset of delamination is observed on the coupons under loading and the maximal load is compared with the performance of a baseline configuration exempt of defects called a “pristine” specimen. 5 specimens per configuration are used for statistical purposes. The compression test plan originally had 0° oriented defects but due to experimental errors this data cannot be used in this work for comparison.

Specimens tested in tension have following naming **AGDD.WW** where DD refers to the number of defects of width 0. WW in embedded in plies of A orientation. Orientation referred to by a star “*” is composed of all three 0°, 45° and 90° orientations. Same thing for specimens tested under compression, though their names start with the letter “C” as summarized below. G stands for “gaps”.

<i>Specimen</i>	<i>No. of defects</i>	<i>Orientation of defects (°)</i>	<i>Defect width (in)</i>
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<i>Pristine</i>	0	/	/
<i>0G4.05</i>	4	0	0.05
<i>0G4.1</i>	4	0	0.1
<i>0G7.05</i>	7	0	0.05
<i>0G7.1</i>	7	0	0.1
<i>0G10.05</i>	10	0	0.05
<i>90G4.05</i>	4	90	0.05
<i>90G7.05</i>	7	90	0.1
<i>45G4.05</i>	4	45	0.05
<i>45G4.1</i>	4	45	0.1
<i>45G7.05</i>	7	45	0.05
<i>45G7.1</i>	7	45	0.1
<i>45G10.05</i>	10	45	0.05
<i>*G4.05</i>	4	0, 45 & 90	0.05

Table 3 Test plan - Tension

<i>Specimen</i>	<i>No. of defects</i>	<i>Orientation of defects (°)</i>	<i>Defect width (in)</i>
<i>Pristine</i>	0	/	/
<i>C90G4.05</i>	4	90	0.05
<i>C90G7.05</i>	7	90	0.1
<i>C45G4.05</i>	4	45	0.05
<i>C45G4.1</i>	4	45	0.1
<i>C45G7.05</i>	7	45	0.05
<i>C45G7.1</i>	7	45	0.1
<i>C45G10.05</i>	10	45	0.05
<i>C*G4.05</i>	4	0, 45 & 90	0.05

Table 4 Test plan - Compression

Defects are embedded at the middle of the specimens along their length. Location of defects through the thickness is shown on Figure 2 below.

Figure 2 Through the thickness distribution of defects for different configurations.

3. TENSILE TESTS

Tensile tests were performed following ASTM-D3039, made for polymer matrix composite coupons where specimens are loaded until failure. All tests are performed at room temperature. Digital Image Correlation (DIC) technique was used to obtain more data at defect locations that are stress concentration points of the tested specimens. In the literature, experimental investigations revealed the minimal effects of a single and isolated defect on mechanical performance, usually less than 5% [6].

Figure 4 Tension 0.1in (2.54mm) wide defects

Figure 3 Failed coupon delamination & fiber failure

Figure 6 Tension 0.05in (1.27mm) wide defects

The more half gap/overlaps there are, the lower the strength is for most of the results. The mix coupon has the lowest normalized strength out of all the coupons with 4 defects. The second weakest configuration is 45D10.05 one, which has an additional 6 defects. The 0 coupons have a rather unexpected result. They are often slightly stronger than the pristine coupon. The difference from the pristine coupons is minimal and therefore this increase of strength might be attributed to the variation of the coupons. The decrease in strength is only larger than 6%

Figure 5 Failed coupon - Large delamination leading to fiber failure [13]

on two occasions (mix and 45D10.05) but that is very unlikely to happen in a real structure.

4. COMPRESSION TESTS

Compression tests were performed following ASTM-D6484 even though our specimens do not have an open hole. ASTM-D6484 is made for polymer matrix composite coupons where specimens are compressed in an anti-buckling fixture until failure. In the literature, it is found that effect of gaps and overlaps on compression performance depends on the location of the defects as well as its area. Up to 12% strength reduction was observed in the literature [6, 11].

Figure 7 Compression 0.05in (1.27mm) wide defects

Figure 10 Compression - 45° oriented defects

The strength reduction for compression tests (average 25%) is more significant than the knock down observed for tensile tests. The more defects, the lower the strength for 45° oriented defects but the opposite is observed for 90° oriented defects. An increased width leads to a higher strength in 45° configurations while it is the opposite for tensile tests. Mixed mode is no longer the weakest configuration. This contrary behavior between tensile and compressive to half gap / half overlap defects may be explained by the locally increased stiffness in fiber direction due to the overlap and the reduced stiffness due to missing fibers at gap area. Thus, there is higher effect on 90° configurations in compression than in tension because the pulling direction is transverse to the

Figure 8 Failed coupon - Delamination and 45° transverse crack

Figure 9 Compression - Typical fracture path

missing fibers. The increase in strength for 90° configurations might also be a cause of waviness that future microscopic observations may reveal.

5. CONCLUSION

Despite the limited data gathered, the test plan and presented results can help build a coherent model able to accurately predict the behavior of half gap / half overlap defects. The major observed result is that compression behavior is more critical than tension and that 45° configurations have larger effects than other configurations, when enough defects are introduced for both tension and compression. Mixed-gap configurations are the least resistant of all configurations in both tension and compression. The effect of the size of the defects is less predictable because the geometry of defects probably change during the cure cycle and compaction. Also, out of plane waviness created by the through the thickness stagger of gaps and overlaps is very likely to have important effects on the mechanical performance.

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